

Materials and Methods for Setting Up and Executing Calibration Runs for Sweep-Width Estimation

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The following describes the materials and methods that the Wadi Qusaybah Survey (Jordan) and Tremithos Valley Survey (Cyprus) used to estimate sweep widths for archaeological survey by fieldwalking (Banning et al. 2011, 2017; Hitchings et al. 2016; Stewart et al. 2016).

Equipment and Materials

Equipment needed includes one to three 50 m tapes, one to four 25 m tapes, stakes to affix the ends of 50 m tapes along the transect route, and a number of tablets (e.g., iPads) or paper forms on clipboards for recording reported artifact locations. Either the camera on the tablet or, if paper forms are used, a separate camera is necessary to document the vegetation cover and other characteristics of the calibration field.

The tablet or recording form should have fields for recording the transect or “pass” number, the identity of the calibration field, the surveyor’s initials, the date, and the start and completion times of the “pass.” In addition, there should be multiple fields where surveyors can record the types of artifacts they think they see, the distances along their transect (in whole meters) at which they saw them, the estimated distance to the artifact, and whether it was to left or right of their path. An example screen using FileMaker Gotm on an iPad appears in fig. 1.

Orange JO 5:42 PM 100%
 Quseiba 2013 Database

Survey Calibration Transects

Next Record Delete

Transect Details

Pass No.: 52 Surveyor: SR - Start Time: 7:06 AM Transect Length: 150 m
 Date Surveyed: 2013/8/21 Ground Cover: Overgrown Olive/Fruit Grove

Finds:

Segment	Distance	Range	L/R	Artifact Class	Segment	Distance	Range	L/R	Artifact Class
1	17	2 m	L	Lithic			m		
2	2	5 m	R	Red Sherd			m		
2	6	2 m	L	Lithic			m		
2	20	1 m	R	Lithic			m		
2	29	2 m	L	Lithic			m		
2	40	1 m	L	Lithic			m		
3	22	3 m	L	Lithic			m		
3	44	2 m	L	Lithic			m		
		m					m		
		m					m		

Finish Time: 7:23 AM Speed: 8.823529 m/min

Notes:

Previous Next Record 101 of 131

Fig. 1. Example of a single “pass” record in a calibration field for the Wadi Qusaybah Survey in northern Jordan. “Segment” refers to the first, second, or third 50 m tape along the surveyor’s route, “Distance” refers to distance along the surveyor’s path, and “Range” refers to the estimated perpendicular distance to left or right of the path.

Other materials needed are multiple artifacts of one or more types, preferably of standardized size or whose size distribution has been recorded and has relatively little spread for each type, resealable bags for sorting and containing the artifacts to make them ready for placement, and copies of maps or coordinates that show where the random placements of artifacts of each type should be.

Pre-fieldwork Preparation

Prior to establishing the calibration fields, managers of the calibration should select or prepare "targets" (e.g., pottery sherds, lithics, nails) that have characteristics, such as size, colour and texture, similar to those of the targets they anticipate surveyors will encounter during survey by fieldwalking. They should be selected to represent the variety of at least the most likely artifacts to be encountered, or perhaps the most important ones, and, for each type, should be fairly consistent in size. It is best to measure them so that their size distributions can later be compared with those of artifacts later detected. There should be enough such artifacts of each type to ensure at least one, and preferably multiples, of each at varying distances from the centre-line. For example, if you anticipate having a 150 m transect, you might want to have four red sherds at each of 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17 and 19 m distance away from the centre-line, randomly distributed among the left and right sides of the "virtual grid". In that event, you would need 40 red sherds. The minimum number (with only one artifact at each distance) would be 10.

Next, you randomly assign the targets to their coordinates. In a basic design for assessing the relationship between distance and artifact detection, that involves a uniform distribution: exactly the same number of artifacts at each distance (e.g., 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17 and 19 m), but randomly assigned to left or right side of the grid, and randomly assigned along the length of the grid. This involves, for each artifact at a given distance, randomly selecting a number from 1 to the maximum of the grid (typically 150), as well as randomly selecting left or right (or 1 or 2). In terms of (x,y) coordinates, length along the grid would be the x-coordinate, while the y-coordinate would vary between -20 and +20 m (to represent left and right sides of the grid).

For some applications, where, for example, it is anticipated that degree of artifact clustering might be an important influence on detection probability, one could use more complex

assignments of artifacts but, for the research reported here, we only used the uniform distribution as described. The coordinates for each artifact type are saved in a different file or tab of a spreadsheet.

Once the assignments are complete, there are two ways to organize the target artifacts for efficient placement. One is to print out the coordinates for each artifact type on a separate sheet, then insert the printed instructions in the bag that contains the relevant type of artifact. The other is instead to organize the artifacts to be placed spatially, for example, to bag the artifacts by sectors of the grid and include in the bag all the artifacts and their coordinates, irrespective of type, that need to be placed in that sector (e.g., x-values of 1 to 25 m on the left side of the centre-line).

Preparation of Field Crew

Before conducting calibration runs, it is important to brief crew members on the procedures and to show them examples of the artifacts for which they are expected to search. At this stage, it is also important to emphasize the importance of surveying “naturally,” at a pace similar to their normal walking speed during actual survey. It is helpful to dissuade them from the impression that their personal performance will be compared with that of others and, to that end, it may be prudent to assign them identification numbers rather than using their real names or initials on the records. If the participants in the calibration treat it as a contest, the results are not likely to be realistic.

Field Methods: Set-up

We have experimented with formally gridded calibration fields, using coloured string fixed in place with large nails, but found this type of set-up was too unnatural for surveyors, even though

it made their assessments of artifact location more accurate. Consequently, we settled on “virtual grids” that are only marked physically by 50 m tapes along the transect route, so that surveyors must estimate the distances of artifacts to the left or right of their path (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. A “virtual grid” on a calibration field of the Wadi Qusaybah Survey in northern Jordan. The thicker white lines show the locations of three 50 m tapes that marked the surveyors’ route and the associated grids are 40 m x 50 m regions (here subdivided into 2.5 m x 2.5 m squares) that were not physically marked but formed the basis for placing artifacts by their random (x,y) coordinates.

It is best to set up a calibration field that previous intensive survey has already “cleared” of ancient artifacts, but whose other characteristics (vegetation cover, plowing, soil type, land use) mimic conditions in parts of the planned survey region fairly closely. It is also best that it be at

least 150 m in length and 45-50 m in width, although it is not absolutely necessary for the transect down the middle to be straight (i.e., there can be slight dog-legs or curves in the transect to accommodate fields that are not rectangular).

We use 50 m tapes to mark the route of the transect, holding the transect ends in place with small stakes, and ensuring that the tape is not twisted so that surveyors will be able to read their distance easily. It is also important that, as much as possible, the tape is down the centre of the field so that there will be adequate room for artifact placements up to 20 m away from it on both sides. As mentioned in the previous paragraph, while placing three 50 m tapes in a straight line is ideal, it is possible to have slight bends or dog-legs along the route if necessary.

One or two people who are not participating in the calibration take the bags containing artifacts to be placed and the list of coordinates and use 25 m tapes extended at right angles from the centre-line, beginning at the appropriate x-coordinate, either left or right of the centre-line depending on whether the y-coordinate is positive or negative. They thus place the appropriate type of artifact in its designated place on the calibration field.

Field Methods: Execution

Once all the artifacts are correctly placed on the “virtual grid,” members of the survey team, each equipped with a tablet or recording form on a clipboard, take turns walking along the route marked by the 50 m tapes. This should be at a pace similar to the walking speed used in actual survey, although we have found that it is sometimes difficult to get crew members to walk at a “natural” speed. Just in case this might be a problem, we record the start and finish times for each “pass,” which then allows calculation of average speed (calculated automatically on the iPad), so we can check to see if deviations from normal walking speed may have been a problem.

As they walk along the transect, they scan the ground to left and right and, when they see one of the target artifacts, they record their longitudinal position by reference to the 50 m tapes and estimate its distance to left or right, recording those coordinates and the artifact type on the digital or physical form. At the end of the transect, it may be necessary to remind them to record their finish time.

Team members make such passes multiple times over a period of days, generally distributed over the course of a survey project, to build up an adequate sample size of observations.

Post-fieldwork Analysis

After collection of data from the calibration fields, detection functions are determined for each artifact type and for all artifact types combined, following the procedures described online via Zenodo at the following persistent URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/10798638> (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10798638).

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